

Table S1. List of specimens included in the analyses and results of the topographic analysis for Dirichlet normal energy (DNE), three-dimensional orientation patch count rotated (3D-OPCR), and relief index (RFI). MorphoSource/ ARCTOS information is given when available. Where specimens are listed as not being used in both analyses, they were only used in the DTA analysis with the exception of the single specimens of *Tupaia picta*, *Tupaia montana*, and *Prodendrogale yunnanica*, which were only included in the GMA.

Specimen ID	Species	Both Analyses?	DNE	3D-OPCR	RFI	DOI/ ARK/ ARCTOS
USNM 481107	<i>Ptilocercus lowii</i>	No	370.128	75.625	0.53767	doi:10.17602/M2/M6391
USNM 488052	<i>Ptilocercus lowii</i>	Yes	379.562	78.125	0.55395	doi:10.17602/M2/M6415
USNM 488055	<i>Ptilocercus lowii</i>	Yes	362.591	76.625	0.56344	doi:10.17602/M2/M6418
USNM 481103	<i>Ptilocercus lowii</i>	No	364.716	75.625	0.5901	doi:10.17602/M2/M6388
USNM 481108	<i>Ptilocercus lowii</i>	Yes	421.374	93	0.59132	doi:10.17602/M2/M6408
YPM MAM 010179	<i>Ptilocercus lowii</i>	No	334.67	71.875	0.538354	ark:/87602/m4/M109160
MCZ 36390	<i>Dendrogale melanura</i>	Yes	343.196	78.875	0.630791	N/A
FMNH 49262	<i>Dendrogale melanura</i>	No	361.815	88.875	0.66367	N/A
FMNH 46630	<i>Dendrogale murina</i>	Yes	317.582	71.25	0.656996	N/A
FMNH 46629	<i>Dendrogale murina</i>	No	300.742	65	0.67611	M12994-22150
UAM:Mamm:103000	<i>Dendrogale murina</i>	No	359.359	63.375	0.64571704	http://arctos.database.museum/guid/UAM:Mamm:103000
AMNH M-103110	<i>Tupaia chrysogaster</i>	Yes	332.942	69.5	0.621501	doi:10.17602/M2/M59520
AMNH M-103093	<i>Tupaia chrysogaster</i>	Yes	309.473	66.875	0.631357	doi:10.17602/M2/M59550
AMNH M-103101	<i>Tupaia chrysogaster</i>	Yes	346.114	70.125	0.647911	doi:10.17602/M2/M58673
AMNH M-103096	<i>Tupaia chrysogaster</i>	Yes	339.482	66.375	0.65322	doi:10.17602/M2/M59075
AMNH M-103095	<i>Tupaia chrysogaster</i>	Yes	357.632	63.875	0.664597	doi:10.17602/M2/M59072
AMNH M-103614	<i>Tupaia salatana</i>	No	295.734	68.75	0.573701	doi:10.17602/M2/M59588
AMNH M-103613	<i>Tupaia salatana</i>	No	285.186	71.125	0.588558	doi:10.17602/M2/M59416
AMNH M-103609	<i>Tupaia salatana</i>	Yes	331.949	67	0.593922	doi:10.17602/M2/M59087
AMNH M-103611	<i>Tupaia salatana</i>	Yes	309.336	63.375	0.624521	doi:10.17602/M2/M59591
AMNH M-103612	<i>Tupaia salatana</i>	Yes	323.095	71.375	0.641161	doi:10.17602/M2/M59078
USNM 311311	<i>Tupaia glis</i>	Yes	306.132	74.375	0.60269	doi:10.17602/M2/M6602
USNM 487950	<i>Tupaia glis</i>	No	303.424	76.125	0.61292	doi:10.17602/M2/M6611
USNM 112662	<i>Tupaia glis</i>	Yes	365.046	70.375	0.66101	doi:10.17602/M2/M6465
USNM 311305	<i>Tupaia glis</i>	No	321.18	71.375	0.66697	doi:10.17602/M2/M6382
USNM 320655	<i>Tupaia belangeri</i>	Yes	377.84	72.625	0.63796	doi:10.17602/M2/M6583
USNM 320690	<i>Tupaia belangeri</i>	Yes	351.873	73.75	0.66499	doi:10.17602/M2/M6608
USNM 320666	<i>Tupaia belangeri</i>	Yes	407.507	77.25	0.67182	doi:10.17602/M2/M6604
USNM 320689	<i>Tupaia belangeri</i>	Yes	389.733	77.125	0.72051	doi:10.17602/M2/M6384
USNM 320680	<i>Tupaia belangeri</i>	Yes	375.359	70.625	0.73313	doi:10.17602/M2/M6606
AMNH M-106110	<i>Tupaia gracilis</i>	Yes	342.648	64.75	0.586241	doi:10.17602/M2/M59409
AMNH M-103619	<i>Tupaia gracilis</i>	Yes	292.991	60.25	0.613209	doi:10.17602/M2/M59379
AMNH M-103620	<i>Tupaia gracilis</i>	Yes	314.55	67.75	0.616572	doi:10.17602/M2/M59373
AMNH M-103850	<i>Tupaia gracilis</i>	Yes	315.06	69.875	0.626239	doi:10.17602/M2/M59350

AMNH M-103892	<i>Tupaia dorsalis</i>	No	347.641	73.375	0.587323	doi:10.17602/M2/M59400
AMNH M-106107	<i>Tupaia dorsalis</i>	Yes	352.666	65.125	0.651864	doi:10.17602/M2/M59370
AMNH M-32631	<i>Tupaia dorsalis</i>	Yes	405.886	65.875	0.655381	doi:10.17602/M2/M59090
AMNH M-106104	<i>Tupaia dorsalis</i>	Yes	401.98	67.5	0.661011	doi:10.17602/M2/M59406
AMNH M-106106	<i>Tupaia dorsalis</i>	Yes	401.208	77.125	0.673387	doi:10.17602/M2/M59361
AMNH M-101670	<i>Tupaia javanica</i>	No	292.809	81.5	0.475056	doi:10.17602/M2/M59364
AMNH M-101663	<i>Tupaia javanica</i>	Yes	343.665	71.625	0.557407	doi:10.17602/M2/M59412
AMNH M-101672	<i>Tupaia javanica</i>	Yes	309.468	67.75	0.567472	doi:10.17602/M2/M59376
AMNH M-101664	<i>Tupaia javanica</i>	Yes	372.709	69.5	0.568756	doi:10.17602/M2/M59367
AMNH M-101832	<i>Tupaia javanica</i>	Yes	345.632	71.125	0.594074	doi:10.17602/M2/M59388
AMNH M-242088	<i>Tupaia palawanensis</i>	No	257.144	72.25	0.465294	doi:10.17602/M2/M59403
AMNH M-207597	<i>Tupaia palawanensis</i>	No	296.412	78.875	0.503431	doi:10.17602/M2/M59397
AMNH M-29725	<i>Tupaia palawanensis</i>	No	347.082	84	0.515167	doi:10.17602/M2/M59391
AMNH M-175465	<i>Tupaia palawanensis</i>	No	322.934	83.875	0.555929	doi:10.17602/M2/M59523
AMNH M-207599	<i>Tupaia palawanensis</i>	No	281.925	71.375	0.571474	doi:10.17602/M2/M59356
FMNH 62948	<i>Tupaia palawanensis</i>	Yes	343.778	66.625	0.64969	M13013-22189
AMNH M-102526	<i>Tupaia minor</i>	Yes	317.232	67.5	0.522606	doi:10.17602/M2/M59382
AMNH M-102527	<i>Tupaia minor</i>	Yes	307.54	67.625	0.539375	doi:10.17602/M2/M59385
AMNH M-103906	<i>Tupaia minor</i>	No	323.261	78.25	0.549639	doi:10.17602/M2/M59353
AMNH M-102529	<i>Tupaia minor</i>	Yes	366.905	69.375	0.574177	doi:10.17602/M2/M59394
FMNH 141464	<i>Tupaia minor</i>	Yes	326.098	72.875	0.61467	M13037-22242
UMZC E.4063.A	<i>Tupaia picta</i>	No	-	-	-	N/A
AMNH M-102830	<i>Tupaia tana</i>	Yes	314.964	62.75	0.586705	doi:10.17602/M2/M59081
AMNH M-102831	<i>Tupaia tana</i>	Yes	264.571	62	0.602236	doi:10.17602/M2/M59084
AMNH M-102829	<i>Tupaia tana</i>	Yes	303.78	67.875	0.613356	doi:10.17602/M2/M59578
AMNH M-102518	<i>Tupaia tana</i>	Yes	349.247	59.25	0.649551	doi:10.17602/M2/M59422
FMNH 68793	<i>Tupaia tana</i>	No	346.772	80.75	0.65349	M13020-22205
UMZC E.4062.A	<i>Tupaia montana</i>	No	-	-	-	N/A
IVPP V20696	<i>Ptilocercus kyllin</i> †	Yes	343.994	66.25	0.551966	N/A
IVPP V8282.13	<i>Prodendrogale yunnanica</i> †	No	-	-	-	N/A